

ON THE OSMOTIC RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN EGG-WHITE AND EGG-YOLK AND THE EFFECTS OF INJECTION OF POTASSIUM CYANIDE AND SODIUM FLUORIDE THEREON.

BY N. M. BASU AND M. C. MITRA.

The average difference in freezing point between egg-yolk and egg-white has been found to be 0.07° . Sodium fluoride solution has been injected underneath the shell and the effects of this injection on the difference in freezing point are noted for 72 hours, showing that the difference in freezing point is reduced from day to day. This difference is accordingly concluded to be not due to Donnan equilibrium between the two sides of the vitellin membrane but is due to a "dynamic steady state" maintained by the vitality of the membrane. The results of injection of potassium cyanide are anomalous and an explanation has been suggested.

A considerable difference in the freezing point between egg-yolk and egg-white was noticed by Straub (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1929, **48**, 49) and this difference is maintained, if the white be diluted and then left in contact with the yolk for 48 hours and exists even if the diluted egg-white be replaced by undiluted egg-white and left in contact with the same yolk for another 48 hours. Hill (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, **26**, 667) showed that the difference in osmotic pressure between yolk and white is roughly about two atmospheres and that the membrane separating the yolk from the white, known as the "vitellin membrane" is extremely thin and permeable to water and the salts of yolk; yet the yolk and the white are not in osmotic equilibrium. The osmotic difference between yolk and white gradually diminishes with age, but the difference is maintained whether the eggs are kept in air or free from oxygen. According to Hill (*loc. cit.*) no true equilibrium exists between the inside and outside of the yolk but a dynamic steady state is maintained as in the case of the nerve or the muscle-fibre. In the case of a nerve or muscle-fibre the potential difference between the inside and the outside is much greater than what can be due to Donnan membrane equilibrium and is maintained so long as oxidation is possible. Accordingly it is concluded that in a nerve or muscle-fibre there is no true equilibrium between the inside and the outside of the fibre, but a dynamic steady state is maintained by oxidation. Johlin (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1932, **16**, 605) found considerable difference in osmotic pressure between the yolk and the white of newly laid eggs but he considered unnecessary the postulation

of a vital activity maintaining a steady state on account of slow establishment of the osmotic equilibrium.

In the present paper attempt has been made to re-examine the whole problem and to find out the effects of injection of potassium cyanide and sodium fluoride on the dynamic steady state, if any, between the yolk and the white, as these reagents are well known inhibitors of oxidation, potassium cyanide inhibiting most types and sodium fluoride inhibiting all types of oxidation.

If the difference in freezing point between the yolk and the white be entirely due to Donnan membrane equilibrium, the disappearance of the biological activity, if any, of the vitellin membrane will not affect it. Accordingly the injection of sodium fluoride, which inhibits the activity of all forms of life, maintained by oxidation, will not affect this difference in freezing point except in so far as would be caused by the distribution of the injected sodium fluoride between the yolk and the white.

If the difference in freezing point be due to dynamic steady state maintained by the biological activity of the vitellin membrane, then, after the injection of sodium fluoride, the difference in freezing point is expected to be reduced.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A number of fresh eggs was taken. In some of them the freezing points of yolk and white were determined so that the average difference in freezing point between the yolk and the white was found. The remaining eggs were divided into two groups, one group being left for control and the eggs in the other group were injected with 0.5 c.c. of a solution containing 0.1 g. of sodium fluoride. Before the injection a hole was made with a sterilised needle on the shell, then 0.5 c.c. of egg-white was removed with a sterilised syringe and the same amount of sodium fluoride solution injected underneath the shell. The hole was immediately plugged with aseptic cotton and collodion. All the eggs were then left in the frigidaire. After 24 hours a control egg and an injected egg were taken out and the freezing points of yolk and white of each were determined. The same process was repeated after 48 hours and 72 hours.

Some difficulty was experienced in the determination of the freezing point of egg-yolk (*cf.* Johlin, *loc. cit.*). When the temperature of the yolk approaches the freezing point, it becomes so viscous that the platinum stirrer, provided with the instrument, detaches itself from the glass rod

TABLE I.

Egg No.	Date of Purchase.	Exam.	Volume of		Freezing point of		Diff.	Remarks
			White.	Yolk.	White.	Yolk.		
I	8-4-37		20 c.c.	15 c.c.	0.47	0.4	0.07	After purchase eggs were kept in frigidaire so as to prevent decomposition.
II	"		20	15	0.56	0.53	0.03	
III	"		16	11.5	0.48	0.41	0.07	After 4 days the same difference in F.P. was maintained.
IV	30-4-37		16	9	0.65	0.58	0.07	
V	20-4-37		15	10	0.48	0.41	0.07	After 24 hours the same difference in F.P. was maintained.
VI	"		15.5	10.5	0.53	0.51	0.02	Injected with 0.5 c.c. of NaF solution containing 0.1 g. of NaF (0.5% soln. of NaF acts as an inhibitor to oxidising enzymes). The diff. in F.P. was reduced after 24 hours.
VII	"		15	10	0.57	0.5	0.07	After 48 hours the same difference in F.P. existed.
VIII	"		16.5	10.5	0.55	0.53	0.02	Injected with NaF soln. on 20-4-37. The diff. in F.P. was reduced after 48 hours.
IX	"		20	15	0.47	0.455	0.015	Injected with NaF soln. on 20-4-37. The diff. in F.P. was reduced after 48 hours.
X	"		20	15	0.47	0.4	0.07	After 72 hours the difference in F.P. still existed.
XI	"		17.5	12	0.54	0.53	0.01	Injected with NaF soln. on 20-4-37. The difference in F.P. was further reduced after 72 hours.
XII	12-4-37		20	15	0.59	0.51	0.07	After 4 days the same difference in F.P. existed.
XIII	"		20	15	0.62	0.51	0.11	Injected with 0.5 c.c. of KCN soln. containing 1 mg. KCN. After 4 days the diff. in F.P. increased.

* An opening was made in egg No VII aseptically and immediately closed by collodion and then kept in frigidaire.

TABLE I (contd.).

Egg No.	Date of Purchase.	Volume of		Freezing point of		Remarks.
		White.	Yolk.	White.	Yolk.	
XIV	12-4-37	20 c.c.	15 c.c.	0.61	0.51	0.1 After 4 days the diff. in F.P. increased.
Duck's eggs.						
A	7-9-37	32	24	2.035	1.995	0.04 Examined after 24 hours.
B	"	36	25	2.24	2.1715	0.0685 " Injected with 1 c.c. of KCN soln. containing 4 mg. of KCN.
C	"	32	24	2.055	2.015	0.04 Examined after 48 hours. The same difference existed.
D	"	37	25	2.075	2.007	0.068 ⁵⁴ " " Injected with KCN soln.
E	"	35	23	2.035	1.99	0.045 Examined after 72 hours. Almost the same difference existed.
F	"	—	—	2.0475	1.98	0.0675 Examined after 72 hours. Injected with KCN soln. Two readings viz. 2.05 and 2.045 were obtained for yolk, the meat, viz. 2.0475 was taken.

G To the white of egg No. E, 1 c.c. of KCN solution containing 4 mg. of KCN was added and the change in F.P. after the addition was noted. It was found that the F. P. increased from 1.99 to 2.

N.B. It is curious that after the injection of KCN to eggs of duck or chicken the difference in F.P. between the yolk and the white increased instead of being diminished. *Vide* eggs no. XIII, B, D and F.

In the experiments noted above care was taken to keep the total amount of the mercury in the bulb constant, when the freezing points of yolk and white of the same egg were determined. The actual zero point was not determined, as the difference in freezing point between yolk and white was noted in these experiments.

during brisk stirring. In order to effect brisk stirring for ensuring uniform freezing throughout the whole liquid, a glass spiral stirrer was made, the length of the spiral being a little less than the column of liquid taken in the inner tube. The yolk was also churned into a homogeneous mass before its freezing point was determined. This is essential for getting consistent results.

Experiments were also made in the same way after the injection of potassium cyanide solution. In the eggs of chicken 0.5 c.c. of solution containing 1 mg. of potassium cyanide was injected. As the results obtained were unexpected, the same experiment was repeated with duck's eggs. In these 1 c.c. of solution containing 4 mg. of potassium cyanide was injected. Before the injection an equal amount of egg white was sucked out by a sterilised syringe.

The results of experiments are given in Table I.

D I S C U S S I O N .

It is obvious from experiments with eggs No. I, III, IV, V, VII, X, and XII that the average difference in F. P. between the yolk and the white, *viz.*, 0.07°, is maintained after 24 hours, 48 hours and also after 96 hours, even if the egg be punctured aseptically and then immediately plugged by cotton and collodion and kept in a refrigerator (*vide* egg No. VII in the Table). Johlin's statement that the osmotic equilibrium is slowly established is not borne out by facts, at least in the case of eggs which were kept in the frigidaire for inhibiting slow decomposition which takes place in air at the ordinary temperature of the laboratory. In egg No. II the difference in the freezing point is only 0.03°. This small difference in freezing point is also noticed in the case of eggs which are not quite fresh. This egg was probably not fresh when it was purchased.

After the injection of sodium fluoride the freezing point of egg-white would be greater than before and, therefore, the difference in freezing point between yolk and white would be less. But as sodium fluoride diffuses into the yolk the concentration of sodium fluoride diminishes in white and increases in yolk. Accordingly the difference (in freezing point) between the yolk and the white would be gradually greater than after the injection. In course of time, while the distribution of sodium fluoride between the yolk and the white comes to an equilibrium, the difference in freezing point between the yolk and the white cannot be so small as it was immediately after the injection of sodium fluoride into the white. When 20 c.c

of the white are mixed with 0.5 c.c. of sodium fluoride solution containing 0.1 g. of the substance, its freezing is actually found to be lowered by 0.045° (approx.), so that after the injection of the sodium fluoride solution the difference in freezing point between the yolk and white, taking 0.07° as the normal average difference, would be $0.07-0.045$ i.e., 0.025° . In the experiments given above it is observed that the difference in freezing point diminishes after 24 hours to 0.02° , after 48 hours to 0.02° or 0.015° , and after 72 hours to 0.01° (*vide* experiments with eggs no. VI, VIII, IX and XI). This gradual diminution in the difference in freezing point between the yolk and the white after the injection of sodium fluoride solution shows clearly that this difference is due to a dynamic steady state maintained by the biological activity of the vitellin membrane, for as soon as this is inhibited by the injected sodium fluoride the difference begins to diminish. This marked diminution in the difference in freezing point cannot in any way be explained as due to the injected sodium fluoride as discussed above.

Experiments with potassium cyanide show curious results. Instead of an expected diminution in difference in freezing point between yolk and white, the difference increased. It is probably due to the action of potassium cyanide after diffusion into the yolk on some of the constituents, in consequence of which it is split up into small molecules. Accordingly its freezing point has been much lowered and the difference between the freezing point of yolk and white has increased.

PHYSIOLOGICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

Received December 6, 1939.
